

International Journal of Microwave Engineering (JMICO)

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Scope & Topic

International Journal of Microwave Engineering (JMICO) is a peer-reviewed, open access journal which invites high quality manuscripts that focuses on Engineering and theory associated with microwave / millimeter-wave technology, guided wave structures, electromagnetic theory and implementation. Authors are invited to submit original research works that stimulate the development of latest technology in industry and academia. Good quality review papers and short communications are also acceptable.

Research areas suitable for publication include, but are not limited to the following fields:

- 2D/3D printed RF and microwave components
- Antenna modelling and measurements
- Channel modelling and propagation
- Cognitive and adaptive radio
- Digital beam forming
- EMI/EMC
- Ferroelectric, ferrite and acoustic wave components
- Hybrid and monolithic active components (amplifiers, mixers, oscillators, etc)
- Methods of maintaining signal integrity
- Micro-machined transmission lines and waveguides
- Microwave and millimetre wave systems
- Microwave device modelling
- Microwave photonics
- MIMO components
- Novel waveguides and new phenomenon in waveguides
- Optical/Fiber techniques
- Passive components (filters, couplers, transitions, etc)
- Phased array
- Radar, SAR and microwave engineering
- Receiver components
- RF MEMs and micro-systems
- RF Nanotechnology: Carbon, semiconductors and other novel material based nanotechnology, nano-devices, meta-materials and nano-scale RF components
- RFID technologies: HF/UHF/RF passive and active RFID tags and readers, printed RFID's
- Signal generation and modulation circuits
- Smart antennas
- THz components and technologies
- Transmitter components
- Wideband and multiband antennas
- Wireless and cellular architectures, circuits and component

Paper Submission

Authors are invited to submit papers for this journal through E-mail: jmicrojournal@airccse.com or [Submission System](#). Submissions must be original and should not have been published previously or be under consideration for publication while being evaluated for this Journal.

Important Dates

- **Submission Deadline : June 04, 2022**
- Notification : July 04, 2022
- Final Manuscript Due : July 12, 2022
- Publication Date : Determined by the Editor-in-Chief

Contact us

Here's where you can reach us: jmicrojournal@airccse.com

Submission System: <https://airccse.com/submission/home.html>